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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE
DEPENDENCE OF EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY ON
SLEEPING PATTERN AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS****¹Dr. Muhammad Usama Anjum, ²Dr. Muhammad Usman Shahid, ³Dr. Muhammad
Roshan Iqbal****¹DHQ Hospital Faisalabad.****Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Physiological control effects the sleep circadian pattern. Cognitive functions of a person are disturbed by variation in this cycle.

Objective: To determine educational efficiency and sleep-wake routine of medical students.

Material and Methods: This research was carried out at Services Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to June 2018) on a total of 258 students. The number of male and female was respectively 108 and 150. Convenient sampling technique was employed for selection. A proforma was designed related to the educational efficiency of students in medical college and their sleeping routine after admission. All the students fulfilled the Proforma. Their premedical efficiency was compared with present performance.

Results: After admission, approximately one fourth (24%) students achieved below 60% marks in exams. They were observed with elevated sleep duration after admission. Most of the students achieved 60% to 70% marks in previous exams. They were observed with reduced sleep duration after admission. No variation in the sleeping pattern was noticed in another one-fourth (23.7%). They earned 70% marks in the examination. In the premedical exams, all the selected students earned more than 85% marks.

Conclusion: As compare to reduced sleep duration, increased timings of sleep in medical college observed more dangerous efficiency of the student is badly influenced any variation in sleeping timings, increase or decrease.

Keywords: Sleep Duration, Circadian, Premedical, Comparison, Exams, Efficiency and Performance.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Muhammad Usama Anjum,**

DHQ Hospital Faisalabad.

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INTRODUCTION:

Internal or environmental aspects set-up the activities of human beings. Physiological functions such as school and work schedule, light and dark cycle, rest and other functions are affected sleep circadian rhythm [1]. According to students, the most depressive time in their life is college life. It is due to the fact that responsibilities, as well as autonomy of students, enhanced remarkably [2]. In college life, the routine of students is disturbed. They are burdened with assignments and feel uneasy with a busy schedule and unordered environment of the hostel. Due to this, the sleep-wake routine of students is disorganized [3]. Learning, memory consolidation and processing of data are affected by the variation in sleeping pattern as it is essential for cognitive restitution [4]. Organism himself organizes sleep-wake cycle which is a circadian pattern. Human beings try to organize a fixed sleeping pattern [2]. Other inner circadian patterns such as deep body temperature and cellular mitosis are similar to the sleep-wake cycle. So, disturbance in the sleeping pattern is associated with internal disconnection, among circadian patterns. This may lead to displeasing effects like performance decrements, issues in attention, somnolence and concentration deficits [4]. Comparative to students who had a stable sleep-wake pattern, excessive day time somnolence is observed in students with unstable sleep-wake pattern [4]. According to some students, disturbance of performance and mood and fatigue results due to an unstable pattern of sleep-wake in 2 – 4 hours [5]. The results of previous research studies indicated that educational efficiency and cognitive issues are strongly linked with bad quality of sleeping [6, 7]. Delayed sleep phase syndrome (DSPS) [2], a circadian disease is a particular issue related to bad educational efficiency. To determine educational efficiency. To determine educational efficiency and

sleep-wake routine of medical students was the objective of this research.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This research was carried out at Services Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to June 2018) on a total of 258 students. The number of male and female was respectively 108 and 150. Convenient sampling technique was employed for selection. A proforma was designed related to the educational efficiency of students in medical college and their sleeping routine after admission. All the students fulfilled the Performa. Their premedical efficiency was compared with present performance. SPSS was used for data assessment.

RESULTS:

After admission, approximately one fourth (24%) students achieved below 60% marks in exams. They were observed with elevated sleep duration after admission. Most of the students achieved 60% to 70% marks in previous exams. They were observed with reduced sleep duration after admission. No variation in the sleeping pattern was noticed in another one-fourth (23.7%). They earned 70% marks in the examination. In the premedical exams, all the selected students earned more than 85% marks. The mean age of the students was (20.2 ± 2) years. After admission, approximately 62 (24%) students achieved below 60% marks in the examination out of 258. They were observed with increased sleep ($> 7 - 8$ hours) duration after admission. 135 (52.3%) students achieved (60 – 70) percent marks in the previous examination. They were observed with reduced sleep duration after admission ($< 7 - 8$ hours). No variation in the sleeping pattern was noticed in the one-fourth (23.7%). They earned 70% marks in exams.

Table – I: Gender and Living Status Stratification

Details		Number	Percentage
Gender	Males	108	42
	Females	150	58
Living Status	Hostilities	50	19
	Day scholars	208	81

Table – II: Mean age, Examination and Sleeping Time

Features	Value
Mean Age	20.2
Pre-medical Examination Marks	Above 85%
Sleeping Time before Admission	7 - 8 hours/day

Table – III: Variation in Sleeping Duration and Result

Number	Percentage	Sleep Hours Variations	Last Exam Marks
135	52.30	Decreased	60% - 70%
62	24.00	Increased	Less than 60%
61	23.70	No change	More than 70%

DISCUSSION:

In college life routine of students is disturbed. They are burdened with assignments and feel uneasy with a busy schedule and unordered environment of the hostel. Due to this, the sleep-wake routine of students is disorganized. In the current study, as compared to sleep timings before admission to medical college, reduced during sleep is observed in half students (52.3%) [3]. As compared to the students with increased sleep timings (< 60% Score), the efficiency (60 – 70) percent of these students were better. But their efficiency is low as compared to students with regular sleep duration (> 705). Moreover, as compared to those with reduced or no change in sleep pattern, less performance is shown by students with increased timings of sleep (<60%). It is surprising fact that among all students, highest efficiency (>70%) is shown by those students who were not found with any variation in sleep duration (23.75) before and after admission to medical college. This indicated that the efficiency of students is badly affected by variation in sleeping routine. A study conducted by Franklin C Brown et al. [2] showed that educational efficiency and cognitive issue are strongly associated with bad sleep quality. Our results are similar to this study. Variations in sleeping routine are observed in most of the participants. Increased and decreased duration of sleep is observed in 24% and 52.3% students respectively. Similar results are noticed in the study by Toras et al. (2005) [3]. In many studies, the effect of sleep deprivation on changing cognitive skills has been discussing. In a study by Brown BJ et al. [8], the influence of overnight calls and sleeping disturbances on surgery residents and medical students was examined. Carskadon [9] determined the influence of changing of the environment from home to college. They observed a reduction in the efficiency of students. It was also been observed that the efficiency of medical students is also reduced by snoring while sleeping.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the efficiency of students is badly influenced by any variation in sleeping time, increase or decrease. The efficiency of students can be increased by setting a stable sleeping plan. Students should follow this plan strictly. This will be helpful in the upcoming life of students as well.

REFERENCES:

1. Browne BJ, Van Susteren T, Onsager DR, Simpson D, Salaymeh B, Condon RE. Influence of sleep deprivation on learning among surgical house staff and medical students. *Surgery*; 115 (5): 604-610
2. Carskadon M A, Davis SS. Sleep-wake patterns in the high-school-to-college transition: preliminary data. *Sleep Research*, 1989; 18: 113.
3. Ficker JH, Wiest GH, Lehnert G, Meyer M, Hahn EG. Are snoring medical students at risk of failing their exams? *Sleep*;22: 205-209.
4. Ana Allen G, José T, Azevedo MH. Sleep-wake patterns and academic performance in university students: Paper presentation: European Conference on Educational Research, University of Lisbon. 11-14 September 2002.
5. Eliasson A, King J, Gould B. Association of sleep and academic performance sleep and breathing. 6: 1, 45-48.
6. Gau SF, Soong WT. Sleep problem of junior high school students in Taipei sleep. 1995; 18:667-673
7. Sadeh A, Raviv A, Grenier R. Sleep patterns & sleep disruption in school-age children. *Dev Psychol*. 2000;17: 129-133
8. Lima PF, Medeiros ALD, Araujo. The sleep-wake pattern of medical students: Early version late class starting time. *Braz J Med Biol Res*. 2002; 35:1373-1377.
10. Brown FC, Soper B, Buboltz Jr. WC. Prevalence of Delayed Sleep Phase Syndrome in University Students. *Coll Student J*. 2001; 35 (3)
11. Taras H, Potts-Datema W. Sleep and student performance at school. *J Sch Health* 2005; 75(7):248-54.